

A STUDY ON INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN BOOLEAN ALGEBRA AND BINARY TREE

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Abstract

One of the important study on graph theory was introduced by Euler in which he solved Electric Network problem in terms of graph. Kirchoff and Cummins developed the theory of tree graph and discussed with their properties. Hu and Tucker have searched optimal binary search tree. Harry introduced graph theoretic terminology. Lu discussed on avoidable & unavoidable trees. Rizzo gave proof of koning's theorem. There are several application related to the study of graphs, tree graph and Boolean algebra into the network problems, electricity problems, designs of decision making problem etc. In this study, we considered Boolean algebra and tree graph and evaluated the variation in the ratio of increment of the number of circuits by adding the parameter of Boolean expression. This problem is useful in the solution of related to the circuit and network problems.

Keywords: Boolean, Binary, Tree.

Introduction

A graph $G = (V, E)$ consists of set of objects $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots\}$ called vertices and another set $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots\}$, whose elements are called edges such that an edge e_k is identified with an unordered pair (u_i, u_j) of vertices.

A tree is connected graph without circuit with the following properties:

- T is connected and circuitless.
- T contains 'n' vertices & 'n-1' edges.
- There is exactly one and only one path between every pair of vertices in T.

A closed walk in which no vertex (except the initial and the final vertex) appears more than once is called a circuit.

Review of Literature

Robert C. Duvall, (2012) The Binary Search Tree is a vital example once teaching knowledge structures. we have a tendency to explore new approaches to understanding the implementation of a Binary Search Tree, victimization ideas from Object-Oriented Programming and C++. The Binary Search Tree illustrates however adopting a brand new approach and a brand new language will cause a brand new approach of brooding about a well-recognized downside.

Michelle L. Wynn, (2013) studied about the molecular networks. As a consequence, there's a crucial ought to develop sensible methodologies for constructing and analyzing molecular networks at a systems level. Mathematical models engineered with continuous differential equations area unit a perfect methodology as a result of they'll give a close image of a network's dynamics. To be prophetic, however, equation models need that various parameters be glorious a priori and this info is sort of ne'er on the market.

Boolean Algebra

Boolean algebra be a non-empty set with two binary operators: addition (+) and multiplication (*) & a unary operation complement (') and two distinct element 0 & 1. The concept of boolean algebra is widely used to design the circuit the graph.

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The circuit graph by the consideration of Boolean algebra of the following Boolean expression is as follows:

$$R = a.b + a.c$$

(where a, b, c are defined as parameters)

Figure 1: Boolean Expression in the Form of Boolean Algebra

If we use figure 1 by considering the concept of graph theory and omitting AND and OR gates then we will obtain the following circuit graph:

Figure 2: Boolean Expression in the Shape of Boolean Tree

Conclusion

It is also concluded that by changing the parameter, the binary tree converts the Boolean circuit and make the network system. To secure the network system, we may analyze any parameter(s) and change accordingly the situation and make the new secure network system. It will help us to convert the parameter into the different meaning and generates the new network path between the different notes and makes the secure system. It is also clear that there is no need to change all parameters. Only change of one parameter, there are lot of situations occurs in the network system. It can solve many problems of network theory related to the security.

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